

Fluctuating Asymmetry Reveals Species-Specific and Metapopulation Responses to Anthropization in Squamates

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Anthropization, through habitat fragmentation and land-use change, is a key driver of biodiversity loss, especially in megadiverse countries like Mexico. Detecting early signs of stress in wildlife is critical for conservation. Fluctuating asymmetry (FA), a deviation from perfect bilateral symmetry, is a sensitive indicator of developmental instability induced by environmental stress. We used geometric morphometrics to assess FA in five sympatric squamate species inhabiting an anthropized landscape in El Cerrillo Piedras Blancas, State of Mexico: *Barisia imbricata*, *Sceloporus grammicus*, *Crotalus triseriatus*, *Thamnophis eques*, and *Thamnophis scalaris*. Standardized photographs of dorsal head views were analyzed using 22 anatomical landmarks. Procrustes ANOVA was used to test for FA; Mahalanobis distances quantified asymmetry magnitude and were compared to centroid size to test for compensatory growth. Additionally, we calculated the Jacobian expansion factor to localize shape changes and constructed a predictive CART model relating FA to environmental variables extracted from satellite imagery. Three species (*B. imbricata*, *T. eques*, and *T. scalaris*) showed significant FA, with no consistent relationship between asymmetry and size, suggesting limited compensatory development. Jacobian maps indicated localized shape instability rather than organism-wide asymmetry. The predictive model explained 30% of the variance in FA and identified key environmental stressors, such as vegetation loss and proximity to agricultural areas. Our results highlight the value of FA as a non-invasive early warning signal of anthropogenic stress in 4 reptiles. This approach enables rapid field assessments and may inform management strategies in protected areas, urban–wildland interfaces, and other vulnerable landscapes.

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